

Ideal orifice pulse tube heat pump performance

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Abstract

The Stirling cycle heat pump is used as an analogy to demonstrate that the maximum heating power per unit input power (also known as the coefficient of performance, or COP) of an ideal orifice pulse tube (OPT) heat pump only approximates to a factor of two for small temperature differences. Although OPTs are widely used in cryogenic refrigeration with great success, they are not suitable for use as domestic heat pumps because of their inherently poor COP.

Keywords: pulse tube, heat pump, efficiency, COP

1. Introduction

Domestic heat pumps are crucial to achieving our climate goals and reducing CO₂ emissions. However, pulse tube cryocoolers have proven to be highly reliable and efficient refrigerators. Recent developments in orifice pulse tube (OPT) cryocoolers have raised the question of whether they can also be used as heat pumps. In this paper, we discuss the fundamental limitations of an ideal OPT for use as a heat pump. As in Kittel [1], we draw an analogy between the Stirling cycle and the OPT cycle. Both the Stirling cycle and the OPT cycle involve oscillating gas flows. For the purposes of this discussion, all thermodynamic quantities are averaged over one cycle. This removes from consideration any effects that average to zero. This approach is valid for ideal lossless devices. However, in practical machines, it can mask losses.

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Figure 1: Schematic representation of the energy and work flow in a Carnot cycle where Q_1 is the heat absorbed at the cold temperature, T_1 , Q_0 is the heat rejected at the hot temperature, T_0 , and W_n is the net work input

2. The Carnot cycle

The ideal Carnot cycle is a good starting point for a discussion of the maximum efficiency of a heat pump. The energy flow for this cycle is shown in Fig.1. From energy conservation:

$$Q_1 + W_n = Q_0 \quad (1)$$

In an ideal lossless system, the entropy is also conserved.

$$Q_1/T_1 = Q_0/T_0 \quad (2)$$

The efficiency (also referred to as COP (coefficient of performance)) is then

$$\epsilon_{hp,Car} = COP_{hp,Car} = Q_0/W_n = T_0/(T_0 - T_1) = 1 + T_1/(T_0 - T_1) \quad (3)$$

where Equations (1) and (2) have been used. The specific power, the input needed per unit of heating is

$$\eta_{hp,Car} = 1/\epsilon_{hp,Car} = (T_0 - T_1)/T_0 \quad (4)$$

As an example, the ideal Carnot cycle for $T_0 = 313K$ and $T_1 = 273K$ has a maximum efficiency $\epsilon_{hp,Car}$ of 7.825. This means that almost 8 times more heat (Q_0) can be generated from the input energy (W_n).

3. OPT and the Stirling cycle

A Stirling heat pump in the α configuration is shown schematically in Fig.2. This heat pump has a warm compressor, a regenerator, two heat

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the α -Stirling and orifice pulse tube heat pumps, where Q_0, Q_1, T_0 and T_1 are as defined in Figure 1 and W_p is the work done by the compressor, W_e is the expansion work recovered and Q_e is the expansion work dissipated (Kittel [1])

exchangers, and a cold expander. The motion of the two pistons is phased to produce a phase shift between the pressure oscillation and the compressor motion. This produces a work flow and cooling in the expander. In an ideal system, the compressor and expander operate isothermally and the system is lossless. The heat absorbed at T_1 is equal to the work done by the cold expander.

$$W_e = Q_1 \quad (5)$$

Then, by conservation of energy, the heat rejected at T_0 is equal to the compression work.

$$W_p = Q_0 \quad (6)$$

If expansion work is recovered, as is the case in an ideal system, the net work output is $W_n = W_p - W_e$ or by substituting Equations (5) and (6)

$$W_n = Q_0 - Q_1 \quad (7)$$

Again in a lossless system, entropy is conserved.

$$Q_1/T_1 = Q_0/T_0 \quad (8)$$

Combining equations (7) and (8) yields the same efficiency/COP and specific power for an ideal Stirling cycle as for the Carnot cycle.

$$\epsilon_{hp,Sti} = COP_{hp,Sti} = Q_0/W_n = T_0/(T_0 - T_1) = 1 + T_1/(T_0 - T_1) \quad (9)$$

and

$$\eta_{hp,Sti} = 1/\epsilon_{hp,Sti} = (T_0 - T_1)/T_0 \quad (10)$$

In an idealized OPT, the cold mechanical piston is replaced by a compressible gas volume within the pulse tube. This volume of gas acts as a displacer, adiabatically transferring work from the cold end to the hot end of the pulse tube. Compressing the gas displacer takes some work, but this is recovered when the displacer re-expands later in the cycle. The mechanical work of expansion transferred to the hot end is not recovered, but is dissipated as heat at the hot end of the pulse tube. The orifice and reservoir provide the phase shift required to produce the work flow. Other than what happens to the expansion work, the ideal OPT behaves just as the Stirling cycle. Thus,

$$W_p = Q_0 - Q_1 \quad (11)$$

W_e is dissipated rather than recovered. So, the net input becomes

$$W_n = W_p \quad (12)$$

The compressible displacer transfers $-Q_1$ via W_e to Q_e . So,

$$-Q_1 = W_e = Q_e \quad (13)$$

Since we consider an ideal system, it is still lossless if we account for Q_e . Thus, entropy is still conserved at both ends of the regenerator

$$Q_1/T_1 = (Q_0 + Q_e)/T_0 = (Q_0 - Q_1)/T_0 \quad (14)$$

Using Equations (11), (13) and (14) results in efficiency and specific power of

$$\epsilon_{hp,OPT} = COP_{hp,OPT} = Q_0/W_n = 1 + T_1/T_0 \quad (15)$$

and

$$\eta_{hp} = 1/(1 + T_1/T_0) \quad (16)$$

This means that the ideal COP of an OPT heat pump approximates a factor of two for small temperature differences, as found, e.g. in domestic heating systems. Although OPTs are widely used in cryogenic refrigeration with great success, they are not suitable for use as domestic heat pumps because of their inherently poor COP.

References

- [1] Peter Kittel, *Ideal orifice pulse tube refrigerator performance*, Cryogenics, Vol 32, No 9, 1992.